

SOCIOLOGICAL DEMOGRAPHIC RESEARCH ON DEMOGRAPHIC DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF FAMILIES

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ABSTRACT

Under the resolution of the UN General Assembly, since 1993, may 15 has been celebrated as international family day. One of the main reasons for the separation of a special day into the family unit is, by the UN definition, "one family is the unity of all human families", it is a small branch of society, a homeland within the homeland.

Introduction

The family is a source of social demographics in the formation of society, ensuring its continuity. The birth of man, the emergence of a new generation, the exchange of offspring occur mainly in the family. All educational and educational environments are provided until a child is born, reaches perfection, and is formed as an individual. A person's relationship with parents, relatives, values, the environment and nature begins at first in the family. At the same time, the family is a social group that delivers tradition from generation to generation.

Each member of society becomes the future heir to this society, shaping the coming generation of young people who will be worthy of the traditions, traditions, and values that are unique to this society. Not only parents, relatives, balconies, other members of that society are also actively involved in this process. We also see this in education, sports, health care, religion and other fields.

As the family is formed and developed in the garden of society, itself is portrayed as a small part of that society. Socio-economic relationships in society also affect family development. In developed countries, the fact that views of family and demographic processes that take place there are unilateral and going remains a troubling situation. On the contrary, demographic activation of people living in developing countries is increasing. It is desirable to choose the development of the family in three directions.

When it comes to family demographic development, it is understood that the amount, formation, and demographic composition of the family change at certain times. The social development of the family, on the other hand, is the improvement of family members' attitudes towards education, tradition, science and culture, nature and society, as well as changes in their social status and health. A change in the family's level of supply of food, clothing, housing and other living items determines its economic progress. It shows that the

family, in its essence, reflects different aspects of society. These sheets, in turn, represent the demographics of the family.

From the time the family was formed to the present day, its types and socio-demographic composition have been changing regularly. Changes in family types and their composition and the factors affecting them should be studied separately for each stage of society's development. The family appears and passes through several stages until it is over. These include the formation of a family (entering into marriage), the birth of their first child (the beginning of childbearing), the birth of the last child, the family of the last child, the descention of a husband or wife who forms the basis of the family from the world, and so on.

The aforementioned processes are the life cycles of the family, regularly returned during the duration of the family, and each of these periods has its own characteristics, socio-economic problems. These socio-economic problems also affect the age of marriage, the number of children, the average life expectancy at birth, and the quality of life.

To study the essence of a family, you need to know its activities, namely, the tasks it performs. One of the most important tasks of the family is the birth of children, namely, the creation of a new generation that ensures the continuity of society. Studying family rearing issues is also one of the most important tasks and is important in raising children by parents, people in the family, and in all aspects of the development of the younger generation. Family arrangements, the relationship between family members, the behavior of parents and others, cultural and political well-being, and family budgets are the main factors in family upbringing. Harmonic rearing of a child cannot be carried out without family rearing. Family upbringing should be combined with social upbringing and strengthened with it, and it is never possible to overlap both forms of upbringing.

The general life of family members with each other in today's form; economic, property, spiritual, psychological relationships; feelings of mutual responsibility are explained by the connection in the vocabulary. Each family member has his or her own social role. Family criteria are divided into three groups.

1. The demographic criterion is mainly expressed through the demographics of the family. There are various manifestations of this criterion, including grouping based on the composition of family members, the status of a husband and wife's family presence, and the number of children.

2. Social criteria are grouped taking into account the social status of family members. Their social origin, occupation, and role in the family are the main manifestations of the criterion.

3. Given the level of economic growth of the economic criterion-family, they are low, medium and fully maintained families.

The performance of family tasks takes place in relation to each other. For example, the healthy birth of children in the family depends on the health of the mother. And the health of the mother and the healthy growth of the child born depends immensely on the level of fulfillment of the economic task of the family, namely, the level of material well-being. In the first place, the development of a child born into a family as a mature person should primarily focus on the education of the child and the formation of a worldview. This process will be incompatible with the performance of the social functions of the family. (Matthew 24:14;

28:19, 20) In turn, an increase in the number of children in the family also affects the level of performance of the family's economic functions. In other words, an increase in family members requires raising the material well-being of the family, that is, accelerating the level of performance of the family's economic function.

The demographic development of the family is mainly studied using statistics. Such data, on the other hand, is collected by regularly registering the family and conducting sociological-demographic (survey) research among the population. Statistics on the family, their system of structure, are not the same in all countries of the world. It depends on the family's concept of statistics and the population list program being conducted, which is recorded for each state statistics. The program is based on the family composition of the population and the types of family residence.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Scientific research of socio-demographic characteristics of the family begins mainly in the 20th century. They were researched by European and American scientists such as M. Elmer, G. Kirkpatrick, R. Hill, T. Fristenson, D. Moge, A. Michel, while research related to the family within the CIS was carried out by Darsky L.E., Bondarskaya G.A., Sifman R.I., Borisov V.A., Kiselova G.P., Belova V.A., Antonov I.A. and others carried out. Many scientists, including Uzbek scientists Jalilov H., Shoumarov B., Bekjonova M., Karakhanov M., Mullajonov I., Studied by Shodiyev R., Boriyeva M. and others. In some sources, the demographic function of the family is called "continuing the generation", while sociologists U.M. Sverdlov, V.A. Ryasensov, V.P. Klyuchnikov "continue the human race", A.G. Kharchev and S.D. Laptенок "restoration of the population", N.G. Yurkevich "giving birth to children" called by names like In the works of these authors, the main focus is on the general study of the socio-demographic characteristics of the family at the republic level, and in the conditions of deepening economic reforms and forming the foundations of civil society, it is necessary to study the socio-demographic characteristics of the family in some regions of Uzbekistan. level scientific studies have not been conducted.

DESCRIPTION OF THE METHODOLOGY USED IN THE RESEARCH

Statistical, observational, mathematical, historical, geographical comparison and extrapolation methods were used in the study of the research topic, as well as a social questionnaire.

MainPart

The use of not only statistical and mathematical methods, but also sociological research methods in researching the demographic development of families serves to further enrich the content of the scientific work. In particular, statistical data expressing the reproductive inclination and desire of the population from demographic processes are not recorded anywhere. This makes conducting sociological demographic research relevant. For this reason, such studies allow obtaining extremely valuable information for regions such as Kashkadarya, whose population consists of local ethnic groups with high demographic potential, and whose traditions and values are valued.

In the process of writing this master's thesis, we conducted several sociological studies. The first sociological study was conducted in Kashkadarya region "How many children should a family have?" was held on the topic of The purpose of our sociological research is to find out

the number of children of reproductive age in Kashkadarya region, i.e. the number of children (boys and girls) planned before starting a family, the number of children after marriage, and how many more children will be born before the end of the reproductive age. In addition to the study of the results related to the planning of development, it is aimed at collecting, analyzing, summarizing and forecasting statistical data in the field of reproductive health and medical geography among the population of the region. As a practical basis of sociological research, we found it necessary to once again show the role and importance of the reproductive rights of the individual.

Taking into account the norms and rules of the sociological demographic research method, researches were conducted in cooperation with the scientific-practical center of Kashkadarya region "Oila". The following results were obtained by taking into account the effects of some circumstances that lead to the birth of children, which are considered among the tasks of the research work. That is, the number of children in the family, whether the father or mother is important in making a decisive decision when they are born, or whether both are equally important, how important is the state's financial support for the father and mother when children are born. it was taken into consideration.

Who is more proactive in family planning (husband or wife), the number of children (boys and girls) and the age difference between the respondents (participants) participating in the research, contraception questions such as the importance and role of contraceptives in family planning and the current state of contraceptive use and who is using them more (husband or wife) were also asked.

By studying the age at which the husband and wife started a family, to study the difference between the age of marriage between those who have passed the reproductive age and those who have just reached the reproductive age, to determine the age at which the first child was born to the respondents (participants, participants) to answer the question of whether they used contraceptives in the first, second, third year of marriage, and if so, what kind of contraceptives they used, and whether or not some of those who did not have children during the last years of marriage had infertility (questions such as determining husband or wife) took an important place.

By studying the opinions of the respondents (participants) about the marriage between relatives, whether their spouse is related to them or not, and if they are related, the physical and psychological effects of children born between relatives it was also necessary to study the level of awareness of the possibility of developmental disabilities and to determine how many respondents (participants) are in mutual marriage with their relatives. To find out who made the main decision when the respondents (participants) entered into marriage (whether they made an independent decision because of their love, whether it was done according to the will of their parents or according to the wishes of their relatives), whether the state provided material support for the birth of children. to study the effects of support, how many more children (boys and girls) they plan to have in the future, and to determine the difference between having children, reproductive behavior assessment, analysis of abortion factors and determination of patterns resulting from abortions.

It should be noted that about 140 people participated as respondents (participants) in this study. All the respondents who participated in this study are residents of cities, towns and

villages of Kashkadarya region. The first question was aimed at determining the age structure of the respondents (participants). We have people under 18 years old-1 percent, 19-24 years old-4.3 percent, 25-29 years old-10 percent, 30-34 years old-13.7 percent, 35-39 years old-20 percent, 40-44 years old -14.3 percent, 45-49 years old - 11.5 percent, 50-54 years old - 11.4 percent, and the number of people over 50 years old - 13 percent.

In a sociological study of the factors of abortion, 40% of respondents were men and 60% were women. It was found that 55% of respondents (participants) live in cities, 32% in rural areas, and 18% in urban-type towns. Considering the national composition of the respondents (participants) by nationality, 75% of them are Uzbeks, 14% Tajiks, 3% Kazakhs, 6% Turkmens, 1% Russians, 1% Arabs, and 1% representatives of other nationalities. . During the analysis of the questionnaires, it was found that 40% of the respondents (participants) who took part in the survey have higher education, 42% have secondary specialized education and 15% have secondary education. It should be noted that among the respondents (participants) with higher education, the majority were specialists in the field of pedagogy.

In the analysis of the family, we found that 38 percent of those who took part in the sociological survey said that their family consisted of 2-4 people, 45 percent of those who took part in the sociological survey said that their family consisted of 5-6 people, the sociological survey 17% of those who participated in the survey indicated that their family was more than 6 people. It was found that 50% of the respondents (participants) were married before the age of 18, 34% at the age of 19-24, and 16% at the age of 25-29. The results of the questionnaire show that 68% of all married respondents started a family under the guidance of their parents and 32% based on their will and love. Currently, 53% of the respondents indicated that they have 3-4 children, 25% have 1-2, and 22% have 5 or more children. Most of the families with 5 or more children exist in families over 40 years old.

During the analysis of the questionnaires, we found out that 32% of the children were 1-2 years old, 60% were 2-3 years old, and 8% were 5 years and older. Question: "Should I use contraception?" 80% of the respondents (participants) said yes and 20% were against contraceptives. However, it was found that some respondents answered yes, but they are not currently using it, or one of the husband and wife is using contraceptives in the family. This is clearly demonstrated by the positive response to all contraceptive questions, including whether you use contraceptives. It was found that 52 percent of respondents (participants) use contraceptives. We found out that the remaining 48 percent of respondents (participant) partially used or did not use contraceptives at all. It is worth noting that 93 percent of respondents (participants) answered that contraception is an important factor in family planning. The remaining 7 percent of respondents (participants) stated that they had not thought about family planning and that they would have children as long as God gave them.

It was found that 61% of the respondents (participants) were from intellectual families, 27% were from working families, and 12% were from working families. When respondents (participants) were asked about the number of family members in their current family, 23% of them live in families consisting of 2-4 people, 55% of 4-6 people, and 22% of 7 or more people. ldi Most of the representatives of families consisting of 2-4 people are young families and it is possible to know whether they live together with their parents or have reached the number of children in family planning. Most of such families responded from families living in

cities. It can be seen that those who believe that the role of grandmother is strong in the upbringing of children of families consisting of 5-6 people, lived together with them. 7 or more family members who live together as family members have mostly reached the end of their reproductive age and most of them have not planned a family and have become childbearing in the proverb "having many children is wealth" knowing that children are a gift from God. there are also families. The large number of children in these families can be explained by the fact that the role of the husband and wife in family planning is fulfilled by the parents of the husband and wife.

How old were you when your first child was born? 6% of respondents (participants) to the question stated that they are 18 years old or under 18 years old. 35% indicated that they were born between 19-24 years old, 33% indicated that they were born between 25-29 years old, 18% indicated that they were born between 30-34 years old, and 8% indicated that they were born between 35-39 years old. How old are your children? 3% of respondents (participants) answered 1 year old, 19% 2 years old, 38% 3 years old, 25% 4 years old, 15% 5 years old.

Would you have another child if you were financially supported by the state? 75% of respondents (participants) answered "yes" and 25% answered "no". Those who answered yes indicated that they had just started having children, while those who answered no indicated that they had the desired number of children or were past reproductive age. What would you like to see in terms of financial support from the state for having a child? 63% of the respondents (participants) answered the question: house, 27% car, and 10% money. As can be seen from the answers given, the main problem in having a child is related to the house. What do you think about marriage between relatives? 98% of the respondents (participants) gave a negative answer to the question, while the remaining 2% gave a positive answer. Would you agree if they offered you to marry your relative? 99.5% of the respondents (participants) answered "no" and 0.5% answered "yes" to the question asked.

Are you related to your spouse? All respondents (participants) answered "no" to the question. Do you know that children born as a result of consanguineous marriages are born with disabilities? 100 percent of respondents (participants) answered "yes" to the question. Why did you answer the above question like that? 63% of the respondents (participants) said that it was because the blood genes of the relatives corresponded to each other, 27% had difficulty answering the question, and the remaining 10% indicated other reasons bitten.

How many more sons do you plan to have from the respondents (participants) in the future? 11 percent of the respondents (participants, participants) said 1, 22 percent 2, 17 percent 3, 31 percent 4, and the remaining 29 percent respondents (participants) said they have no plans. How many girls do you plan to have in the future from the respondent (participant)? 33% of the respondents (participants, participants) said 1, 27% 2, 10% 3, 3% 4, and the remaining 27% of the respondents (participants) said they have no plans.

How old do you plan your children to be? 7% of respondents (participants) indicated 1 year, 39% 2 years, 44% 3 years, 5% 4 years, 5% 5 years. How old do you plan to be between your oldest and youngest children? 1 percent of respondents (participants) indicated that they were 1 year old, 27 percent were 2 years old, 49 percent were 3 years old, 23 percent were 4 years old, and 1 percent were 5 years old. Most of the respondents (participants) in

family planning said that contraceptives always gave a high level of reliable results in controlling the birth of children with their partners, and some respondents (participants) still use them (women and men).) have shown that it has positive aspects in family stability.

Some respondents (participants) indicated that they are not currently using contraceptives, but during the period when they used them regularly, their importance in family planning was high. To the question "Who plays an important role in family planning", 75% of the respondents (participants) indicated that they make decisions together. 20% of the respondents (participants) indicated that men play the main role, and the remaining 5% indicated that the main role is played by women. Later, we started to create a platform for the "online test" program for sociological study of the factors of abortion. In the process of sociological research, the causes and conditions of abortion were studied. 3 respondents participated in the study. It should be noted that 18-29 (2) and 30-39 (1) of the respondent (participant). 2 of them are working and 1 is studying at a higher education institution.

The first and second respondents are married and both live in the city. One respondent lives in a village. Two of the respondents (participant) have completed the bachelor's (incomplete) stage of higher education and one is studying at the master's level. Two of the respondents (participants) have no children at all, and one has 2 children. Respondents (participant) 2 respondents answered the question "How many abortions have you had?" The first respondent (participant) stated that she had one abortion and no other abortions. Abortions were performed before the fourth week of pregnancy and were done because of mothers' health, pressure from relatives, and unwillingness to have children.

It should be noted that in the matter of abortion, 2 respondents supported their desire, and one respondent added that he did not ask the opinion of his partner's family. In abortion, the surgical method is mainly used and it is recommended by the doctor. All three respondents answered that they did not use contraceptives to prevent pregnancy at all. These are related to the tools used: condoms, hormonal drugs, hormonal patch, hormonal ring, broken bonds. Respondents (participant) said that they use contraceptives and all their types to avoid pregnancy in the future. One respondent stated that it caused an ectopic pregnancy. One respondent (participant) stated that he was depressed. All three respondents (participant, participant) said that they did not have breast cancer and were not pregnant. Also, the implementation of this process is related to family education.

Conclusions

In the socio-demographic development of families of the Kashkadarya region, birth control measures should include the following:

- improving the quality of the population, increasing the activity of women in general and professional education;
- employment measures and development of urbanization;
- increase the living standard and quality of citizens of the republic;
- strengthening the influence of the state on the behavior of the family, work team, and the individual;
- family and marriage strengthening, etc.

It is appropriate to allocate funds from the state budget, as well as funds from the UN Population Fund and the Fund for the Development of Women's Issues and other

international financial institutions for the implementation program of the demographic policy concept.

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